

Gliding and parachuting by arboreal salamanders

Specimen Collectors: Christian E. Brown, CADFW Scientific Collection Permit #13153.

Data Collectors: Christian E. Brown and Erik A. Sathe, IACUC Protocol: USF IS0004512

Hardware: One vertical wind-tunnel (MIDIMASTER Eco, Siemens), three cameras (Fastec HiSpec, 400 Hz), one laptop with an external hard-drive for storage space (Seagate Plus).

Software: DLTdv Version 7 Digitizing Tool (Hedrick, 2018) available from <http://biomech.web.unc.edu/dltdv/> and MATLAB for calculating kinematics. Kinematics code has been submitted to Am. Nat. along with this naturalist.

File Format: All recorded wind tunnel trials were saved in .MOV format, and all position data was saved in .xls or .csv formats. Position data was originally measured in pixels, converted to X,Y,Z positions, smoothed, and analyzed for kinematics.

File Names: All wind tunnel trials were conducted in December of 2018 at room temperature.

Video file-names as well as data file-names follow this general scheme:

“Camera view1_Camera view 2_Salamander #_s0001_Trial #”

(e.g. FRNT_TOPP_AV21_s0001_tT03 represents the Front and Top camera views of *Aneides vagrans* individual number 21 during the 3rd trial of that salamander).